
EDUCATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF K. B. P. COLLEGE VASHI, NAVI MUMBAI**Dr. B. M. Munde***Department of Economics,**Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil College Vashi, Navi Mumbai (Maharashtra)*

Abstract

Education system must be based on quality, accessibility, affordability and ethics. No doubt, governments have taken various steps to make education inclusive in our country. Subsequently literacy rate jumped up from 18.30 percent to 74.04 percent during 1951 to 2011. However, as far as quality, accessibility, affordability and ethics are concerned, situation is not satisfactory in our country. The education particularly after new economic reforms of 1991 is commercialising. It is not affordable to the people in countries like India where sizable part of the population is struggling for the 'Bread and Butter'. The Higher Education System in India compared to developed countries needs substantial improvement. The enrolment ratio is hardly about 13 percent whereas the same is varying between 28 to 90 percent across the world. Budget allocation for education by Govt. of India in 2012 was about 6 percent of total expenditure, which is not going to be adequate, and therefore allocation must be made appropriately, i.e. minimum 10 percent in order to improve the educational scenario in India. Basic education must reach to maximum number of children from different strata of the society so that they will be eligible to pursue higher education. Furthermore, in higher education too, due to commercialisation, there is major problem of universal economic accessibility, affordability and more importantly, quality of education. In this Situation, in last five academic years (2011-12 to 2015-16), how is the Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil College Vashi, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra carrying social responsibility in providing higher education to the students from economically lower or middle strata of the society? It is analysed in this research paper.

Key words: *Enrolment ratio, social commitment, economic accessibility and affordability.*

1. Introduction

The present education system in India has come a long way and the age old traditions have undergone a new makeover. Government of India/ State Governments/ Local Governments are taking efforts in this field so that the objective of inclusive growth can be achieved very soon. A great achievement of the governments is a big jump in the literacy rate from 18.3 percent in 1950-51 to 74.04 percent in 2010-11. Such an achievement is the result of many efforts by the Indian government in education sector. The government is improving the country's education status to enhance the standard of living of the people and to achieve other goals like, overcoming the problem of poverty and unemployment, social equality, equal income distribution, etc. Education contributes to the individual's well-being as well as the overall development of the country. Education is not only an instrument of enhancing efficiency but is also an effective tool of widening and augmenting democratic participation and upgrading the overall quality of individual and societal life (Goel, 2008). Thus, the importance of education cannot be ignored. However, it is not equally available to all Indians. Existing system deny economic accessibility to the deprived section of the society. Still, some education institution like Rayat Shikshan Sanstha , Satara , Maharashtra are taking strong efforts to make education available to those who are denied by the profit making educational institutions in both rural and urban areas.

2. About Rayat Shikshan Sanstha and Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil

Rayat Shikshan Sanstha, Satara, is Asia's largest educational institute with over 689 branches which includes

43 colleges, 438 secondary schools, 8 training colleges, 28 primary schools, 68 cosmopolitan hostels, 7 administrative offices, 8 Ashram schools, 2 ITIs, 1 Engineering College, 57 Ancillary branches etc. spread over 14 Districts of Maharashtra and 01 District of Karnataka. Recently 4.42 Lakh students are pursuing education at various levels and their care is taken by 17363 teaching and non-teaching staff. It is based on the thoughts of Mahatma Phule, Rajarshi Shahu Maharaj, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar and Mahatma Gandhi. The Sanstha was established in 1919 by Padmabhushan Late Dr. Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil. He worked to uplift the rural, uneducated masses and downtrodden through education. He literally carried the lowly, pitiable, helpless and smart boys on his own shoulders and educated them. Some of them became Barristers and Vice-Chancellors in their later career.

Under the Chairmanship of Hon. Dr. Anil Patil, stalwart educationist and Social thinker, the Sanstha is now focusing on providing life skill development, technical advancement and competitive examination guidance to our students. The purpose is to make them responsible citizens and enhance the employability of our students. On the whole, the Sanstha aims at imparting liberal and vocational education from pre-primary to the university level, focusing more on the downtrodden, economically and socially backward sections of the society and tries to enrich the dignity of labour.

Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil College Vashi, Navi Mumbai is one of the most flourishing branches of the Rayat Shikshan Sanstha and well reputed in the University of Mumbai. Since its inception in 1979, the college has been galloping towards academics, quality education and infrastructural accomplishment.

Today, the college imparts quality education in various faculties, viz. Arts, Commerce, Science, and Management. It also runs information Technology, Computer Science, Biotechnology at degree level. Information Technology, Computer Science, Biotechnology, Chemistry, Microbiology, Mathematics, Physics and in Business Economics are run at P. G. Level. Besides these, B. Lib., M. Lib. and M.B.A. courses affiliated to Yashwantrao Chavan Maharashtra Open University, Nasik are available in the College.

3. Objectives of the Research

1. To analyse academic performance of under graduate students of Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil College of last five academic years (2011-12 to 2015-16).
2. To analyse an annual income of the parents.

4. Research Methodology

This research paper is based on secondary data provided by student/parents in the registration form while taking admission at first year classes of different streams. It was tabulated chronically and statistical tools like percentage, average are used to analyse data according to objectives of the research.

5. Limitations of the Study

As data is collected from application forms which were filled by either students or their parents at the time of admission, there is possibility to show low income in expectation of getting concession in the fees, scholarships and other facilities from Governments or College.

Table no. 01 shows that the proportion of the students, whose performance is improved at the third year class as compared to H.S.C. is increasing except academic years 2012-13 and 2014-15. Its trend was 49.90 percent, 37.39 percent, 56.56 percent 45.74 percent and 61.22 percent respectively during the analysis period. On an average 50.16 percent students improved their percentage at third year class as compare to percentage of H.S.C. It also shows that, the girl students for all streams are comparatively more than boys-students. Outside students average ratio was 2.42 percent and it is hovering between 2 percent to 7 percent during the same period for various streams.

6. Economic and Educational Analysis

- I. Table no. 01 shows that the proportion of the students, whose performance is improved at third year class as compare to H.S.C. is increasing except academic years 2012-13 and 2014-15. Its trend was 49.90 percent, 37.39 percent, 56.56 percent, 45.74 percent and 61.22 percent respectively during the analysis period. On an average 50.16 percent students have shown improvement in their performance at the third year class as compared to performance of H.S.C. However, there is enough scope for academic performance improvement in future.
- II. It is noteworthy that female students are more in number as compare to male students for all streams during the analysis period. It implies that College provides safety environment to the female students.
- III. Outside students' average ratio was 2.42 percent and it was hovering range between 2 percent to 7 percent during the same period.

K. B. P. College is providing higher education to the students who belong to lower income group (Average annual income of parents was Rs.

7. Conclusion

The Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil College is providing education to the students who are from low income group. It shows its commitment towards the deprived group of the society. The College also provides safety environment to the female students and outsiders. It implies that, even though the College is located in Metropolitan City of the 21st century, still, it is closely in touch with founder's vision and trying to meet the economic gap between the rich and the poor of the society. However, it also has an enough scope for improvement in quality of education.

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